

Soil and Crop Management

Response of rice to N split application on a saline soil

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This study in IRRI's soil chemistry greenhouse used soil samples taken from Kalawagan, Pangasinan, Philippines. The soil was nonsaline, nonsodic, low in organic matter, and had a pH of 7.4. Sodium chloride was used to obtain soil solution EC, values of 2.8, 4.8, 8.2, 10.0, and 13.4 dS/m at 25 °C. IR56 seedlings were planted.

The soils were fertilized with superphosphate and muriate of potash at 25 mg/kg. Basal N as urea was applied as 25, 25, 50, and 100 mg N/kg. The two 25 mg/kg levels received additional urea at 50 and 100 mg N/kg at panicle initiation. The 4

Effect, of 5 salt and 4 N levels on yield. IRRI greenhouse.

Salt level (dS/m)	Shoot av (g/pot)	Straw av (g/pot)	Grain ^a (g/pot)				Mean
			50	75 ^b	100	125 ^b	
ECe 2.8	17.6	16.5	17.2 a	22.6 a	17.5 a	25.9 a	20.8
ECe 4.8	13.3	14.1	13.0 b	21.3 a	14.3 b	22.2 b	17.7
ECe 8.2	5.2	8.6	4.4 c	8.5 b	3.5 c	6.5 c	5.7
ECe 10.0	2.2	4.4	2.1 d	3.8 c	0.6 d	1.0 d	1.9
ECe 13.4	0.6	0.0	0.0 d	0.0 d	0.0 d	0.0 d	0.0
Mean	7.8	8.7	7.4	11.2	7.2	11.1	9.2

^aIn a column figures followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^bSplit application: (25 basal + 50 mg/kg topdressed) or (25 basal + 100 mg/kg topdressed).

levels of N finally imposed were 50, 75, 100, and 125 mg/kg.

Regardless of the amount and timing of N, increasing salinity levels strongly affected yields from EC, 8.2 to 10.0 dS/m (see table). At EC, 13.4 dS/m, plants died.

The yield reduction may be attributed to the effects of salinity on

the yield-contributing characters. Plant height, tiller numbers, panicle weight, and 1,000-grain weight were affected.

N did not significantly affect shoot weight. However, the straw and grain yields differed with basal and split N applications. In saline conditions, topdressed nitrogen was more efficient than basal application. □

Efficiency of urea-based fertilizers in coastal rice

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We evaluated the efficiency of urea-based N fertilizers in midland soil of coastal Karnataka. The experimental field was fine, loamy, mixed-isohyperthermic family of Ustoxtropepts with pH 5.1, 1.26% organic C, and 78 kg P and 50 kg available K/ha. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with four replications.

Medium-duration IET3232 26-d-old seedlings were transplanted on 17 Jul 1984 at 20- × 10-cm spacing, 3 seedlings/hill. Plots were treated with

Urea-based fertilizers' effects on grain yield and N uptake. Mangalore, India, 1984.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers/m ²	Grain wt (g/hill)	N uptake (kg/ha)
Control	3.7	385	7.7	73
Urea split (50% basal + 25% tillering + 25% panicle initiation)	4.7	493	9.1	92
Urea basal application	4.4	500	9.0	88
Lac-coated urea	5.1	485	10.3	94
Neem cake-blended urea	5.1	458	10.0	91
Green manure + urea (1:1)	4.9	458	9.8	90
CD (0.05)	0.7	59	1.4	-

^a Urea at the rate of 90 kg N/ha.

75 kg superphosphate and 90 kg muriate of potash/ha and kept flooded from transplanting to harvest. Pests and diseases were controlled. Harvest was on 6 Nov 84.

Five N sources were tested (see table). Yield and its attributes differed significantly with N source. Maximum grain yield with neem cake-blended

urea and lac-coated urea was statistically significant. Split application of urea was more productive than basal application. Yields with green manure + urea (1:1) at planting were comparable to those with coated urea. N uptake was higher with coated urea than with conventional urea applied basal. □